

Tube: wt

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	811,484	###	100.0
visible	702,123	86.5	86.5
intact	313,630	44.7	38.6
mCherry	19	0.0	0.0
singlet sort	9	47.4	0.0

Experiment Name: 061015 ruth mCherry
 Specimen Name: Specimen_001
 Tube Name: wt
 Record Date: Oct 6, 2015 12:02:35 PM
 \$OP: Administrator

Population	#Events	%Parent	PE-Texas R... Mean	Alexa Fluor ... Mean
intact	313,630	44.7	354	299
mCherry	19	0.0	4,044	268
singlet sort	9	47.4	4,393	237

Tube: mCherry+SG_11

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	797,870	###	100.0
visible	763,534	95.7	95.7
intact	554,865	72.7	69.5
mCherry	809	0.1	0.1
singlet sort	487	60.2	0.1

Experiment Name: 061015 ruth mCherry
 Specimen Name: Specimen_001
 Tube Name: mCherry+SG_11
 Record Date: Oct 6, 2015 11:48:40 AM
 \$OP: Administrator

Population	#Events	%Parent	PE-Texas R... Mean	Alexa Fluor ... Mean
intact	554,865	72.7	234	215
mCherry	809	0.1	2,776	204
singlet sort	487	60.2	2,445	174